

THE USE OF STORYTELLING, ROLE-PLAY, AND PROBLEM-BASED SITUATION TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SOFT SKILLS

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Abstract. *This article explores the theoretical and practical aspects of developing soft skills among students majoring in preschool education. In the context of globalization, the global education system increasingly emphasizes not only students' academic knowledge but also the development of essential competencies such as communication, critical thinking, and social adaptability. Therefore, the use of interactive teaching methods has become widespread in the education systems of developed countries. In particular, storytelling, role-playing, and problem-based situation technologies are considered effective tools for enhancing students' practical and social skills.*

The article provides a scientific analysis of the pedagogical potential of these methods and their role in the formation of soft skills. The main objective of the experimental study was to determine the effectiveness of interactive methods in developing soft skills among students of the preschool education program. During the instructional process, experimental activities were organized, and students' performance was evaluated based on specific criteria.

The results demonstrate that the systematic integration of these methods into the educational process significantly improves students' communication, empathy, critical thinking, and teamwork skills. In addition, traditional and interactive teaching approaches were compared, and the advantages of modern methodologies were substantiated.

The study is of considerable importance for improving the educational process in higher pedagogical institutions and contributes to the development of professional competencies of future educators. Furthermore, this work is significant in that it expands the possibilities of developing soft skills through the integrated application of interactive methods.

Keywords: *soft skills, storytelling, role-playing, problem-based learning, interactive methods, preschool education, empathy, critical thinking, pedagogical innovations, professional competence.*

Introduction

One of the key directions in the development of the modern education system is not only the enhancement of learners' knowledge but also the development of their social and communicative competencies. Therefore, the formation of soft skills has become a priority in contemporary global education policy.

In international practice, particularly in developed countries, teaching technologies based on storytelling, role-playing, and problem-based situations have been widely integrated into the educational process. Through these methods, students not only acquire knowledge but also develop the ability to act effectively in real-life situations. The effectiveness of storytelling technologies has been confirmed in numerous international studies [9]. In particular, the American scholar J. Bruner, who conducted research at Harvard and later at Oxford University, emphasized the

importance of narrative-based instruction, stating that “human thinking is shaped through events and stories; therefore, a narrative approach plays a crucial role in the educational process” [1]. As noted above, presenting events in a more engaging and expressive manner, rather than merely describing them briefly, makes communication more interesting for the listener and helps to capture their full attention.

The scientific foundations of the role-playing method were developed by L. S. Vygotsky, who considered play activity as an essential means of acquiring social experience [3]. The problem-based learning approach is often associated with the American educator J. Dewey, who worked at Columbia University and argued that the educational process should be oriented toward solving real-world problems [2].

In Central Asian countries, attention to these approaches has been increasing as part of ongoing educational system modernization. In Uzbekistan, within the framework of preschool education development, large-scale efforts are being implemented to introduce innovative pedagogical technologies. However, practice shows that although students majoring in preschool education possess sufficient theoretical knowledge, their skills in applying this knowledge in real pedagogical situations, effective communication, and problem-solving remain insufficiently developed. This issue determines the relevance of the present study.

Methodology

The study analyzes the theoretical foundations and practical applications of storytelling, role-playing, and problem-based situation technologies as pedagogical approaches. The storytelling method, grounded in Bruner’s narrative approach, enables students to develop thinking skills, identify problems within events, and express meaningful ideas through structured narration and event analysis. As a practical example, students engage in exercises where they listen to conflict situations occurring in preschool settings presented in story form and then develop possible solutions.

At the same time, the role-playing method is based on Vygotsky’s (1978) theory of social learning and Kolb’s (1984) experiential learning model. Through this approach, students assume various pedagogical roles (teacher, child, parent), which allows them to strengthen their problem-solving and communication skills in real-life situations. For instance, by simulating tasks such as classroom management, providing guidance to children, or coordinating classroom activities, students develop collaboration, empathy, and teamwork skills.

The problem-based situation technology is aligned with Dewey’s (1938) concept of experiential education and directs students toward analyzing real pedagogical problems, comparing alternative solutions, and making reasoned decisions. For example, students are presented with pedagogical scenarios such as “lack of attention among children” or “low motivation” and are required to develop strategies to address these issues.

Thus, when integrated, storytelling, role-playing, and problem-based situation technologies collectively contribute to the development of soft skills, including communication, critical thinking, empathy, and teamwork. The study primarily focuses on the pedagogical potential of these methods, their implementation strategies in student learning, and their application within interactive instructional settings.

Results

The experimental study was conducted with the participation of students enrolled in the preschool education program at Andijan State Pedagogical Institute. Second- and third-year

students took part in the study and were divided into experimental and control groups. The process was organized in three stages: initial diagnostics, experimental intervention, and final analysis.

At the initial stage, students' soft skills were assessed through observation, interviews, and practical tasks. During the evaluation process, students' communicative competence, empathy, critical thinking, and teamwork skills were analyzed based on specific criteria. Each skill was assessed using a 5-point scale, which made it possible to determine the students' initial level. This, in turn, allowed for comparison of changes in subsequent stages.

During the instructional process, interactive methods were systematically applied. Unlike traditional approaches, classes were organized based on problem-based situations, encouraging active student participation [5]. In the storytelling method, pedagogically meaningful situations were presented in narrative form, prompting students to continue the story, develop alternative solutions, and justify their opinions.

In role-playing activities, students were divided into small groups and assigned specific pedagogical roles. They discussed the given situations individually and collaboratively, attempting to develop multiple solution options. In addition, the reflection method was applied throughout the process, enabling students to analyze their own performance, recognize mistakes, and develop self-improvement skills [4]. This contributed to a deeper formation of soft skills.

In the control group, the learning process was conducted in a traditional format of lectures and question-and-answer sessions, with limited use of interactive methods. This provided an opportunity to compare the results.

The analysis of the results obtained at the end of the experimental process showed that the learning process organized on the basis of interactive methods had a significantly positive impact on the development of students' soft skills. A comparison of initial and final indicators revealed a clear positive growth dynamic, especially in the experimental group.

According to the analysis based on evaluation criteria, students in the experimental group demonstrated significant improvement in communicative skills compared to their initial level. Their ability to actively participate in lessons, express their thoughts freely, and interact within a group improved considerably. Students not only learned to express their own ideas but also developed the culture of listening to others and participating in discussions.

Positive changes were also observed in empathy skills. Through role-playing activities, students attempted to understand others' emotions by performing various social roles. As a result, they learned to approach pedagogical situations more carefully and consciously. This was particularly evident in resolving conflict situations.

The development of critical thinking skills was directly associated with problem-based learning technologies. Students learned to analyze situations not only superficially but also in depth, identify cause-and-effect relationships, and develop multiple solution options. Most importantly, they attempted to justify each solution, which indicates an improvement in their logical thinking abilities.

Teamwork skills also improved significantly. During group tasks and role-playing activities, students learned to collaborate, distribute responsibilities, and work together to achieve common goals. This increased their social adaptability.

A general analysis of the results showed that while steady growth was observed across all indicators in the experimental group, no such significant changes were recorded in the control group. Students in the control group were largely limited to theoretical knowledge, and the development of practical skills remained relatively weak.

Furthermore, observations indicated that students in the experimental group showed increased interest in the learning process. They became more active in classes and began to express independent opinions. This also demonstrates the motivational significance of interactive methods [6].

Based on the obtained results, it can be concluded that the integrated use of storytelling, role-playing, and problem-based learning technologies is highly effective in developing students' soft skills [7]. In particular, these methods transform students' passive participation in the learning process into active engagement and bring them closer to real pedagogical practice. The results confirm previous scientific views on the effectiveness of interactive methods and justify their application in preschool education programs.

Discussion.

The analysis of the obtained results shows that traditional approaches are not sufficiently effective in developing soft skills among students of preschool education. In my opinion, the main reason for this is that the educational process is largely theory-oriented and does not adequately focus on preparing students for real pedagogical situations.

According to our observations, when storytelling, role-playing, and problem-based learning technologies are introduced into the educational process, student engagement increases significantly. In particular, lessons organized around storytelling encourage students to think more actively, as they are required to participate in understanding and continuing the sequence of events. In my view, this approach develops not only students' knowledge but also their imagination and creative thinking.

During role-playing activities, students have the opportunity to perceive themselves as future educators. This helps to connect theoretical knowledge with practical application [8]. This aspect is one of the key factors in developing soft skills, as students learn to make decisions in situations close to real-life contexts.

As for problem-based learning technology, this method encourages students to think independently and compare different perspectives. Our observations indicate that this approach contributes to the development of students' critical thinking skills and aligns well with the requirements of modern education.

In addition, interactive methods have a positive impact on the formation of social relationships among students. They learn to listen to each other, exchange ideas, and work collaboratively. These skills are of great importance in their future pedagogical activities.

When comparing the obtained results with existing scientific theories, it can be noted that they are largely consistent with previously proposed views. In particular, ideas related to the effectiveness of storytelling-based instruction and developmental teaching approaches are in line with the findings of this study. However, in my opinion, the comprehensive application of these methods specifically in preschool education has not yet been sufficiently explored, and further in-depth research in this area is needed.

From this perspective, the results of the study not only confirm existing theories but also enrich them in practical terms. In particular, the integrated use of storytelling, role-playing, and problem-based learning technologies has proven to be highly effective in developing students' soft skills.

In modern education, increasing student engagement and fostering independent thinking remain priority tasks. Interactive methods provide effective opportunities to achieve these goals [9].

Conclusion

Within the framework of this experimental study, the effectiveness of storytelling, role-playing, and problem-based learning technologies in developing soft skills among preschool education students was investigated. The results of the study indicate that the systematic integration of these methods into the educational process is an important factor in the development of students' personal and professional competencies.

The analysis revealed that while traditional teaching methods tend to shape students as passive listeners, interactive methods transform them into active participants. In particular, the use of storytelling contributed to the development of students' thinking, their ability to analyze events, and to express meaningful ideas. Role-playing activities enhanced their ability to behave appropriately in real pedagogical situations, engage in communication, and solve problems effectively.

Lessons organized on the basis of problem-based learning technology taught students to think independently, compare different solutions, and make well-reasoned decisions. This, in turn, had a direct impact on the development of critical thinking skills. At the same time, through group work activities, students acquired teamwork skills, collaboration abilities, and principles of mutual respect.

The obtained results confirm that theoretical knowledge alone is not sufficient for the development of soft skills; rather, practice-oriented methods play a decisive role. From this perspective, the integrated use of storytelling, role-playing, and problem-based learning technologies can be considered an effective modern pedagogical approach.

The scientific novelty of this study lies in the комплекс (integrated) application of these methods and in substantiating their combined effectiveness in developing students' soft skills. From a practical standpoint, the results of the research can be applied to improve the educational process in higher pedagogical institutions.

Based on the conducted research, the following recommendations can be proposed:

- systematic implementation of interactive methods in the educational process;
- organization of lessons based on real-life situations;
- encouraging students to think independently and make decisions;
- development of clear criteria for assessing soft skills.

In conclusion, it can be stated that in the modern education system, the formation of competitive, creative, and communicative individuals is a priority task, and the role of interactive methods in this process is invaluable. In my opinion, it is precisely through such approaches that the professional potential of future educators can be further enhanced.

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